

THE USE OF COMPOSITES IN SEISMIC RETROFITTING OF MASONRY WALLS

John C. Jai¹, Rita M. Kiss², László P. Kollár², Helmut Krawinkler³, and George S. Springer¹

¹*Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Stanford University, Stanford, CA, USA*

²*Department of Civil Engineering, Technical University of Budapest, Budapest, Hungary*

³*Department of Civil Engineering, Stanford University, Stanford, CA, USA*

SUMMARY: A procedure was developed for estimating the effectiveness of composite materials in retrofitting masonry walls subjected to in-plane normal and shear loads. The reinforcement may be continuous fiber composites or fibrous mats applied to the wall in a wallpaper-like fashion. The walls may have one or more openings such as windows and doors. The model provides the load set and the deflection of the wall at failure. A parametric study is also presented illustrating the effectiveness of the reinforcement in strengthening masonry walls. This study shows that composite reinforcement may prove to be an effective method of reducing damage to masonry walls during earthquakes.

KEYWORDS: infrastructure, masonry, seismic retrofitting

INTRODUCTION

The collapse of unreinforced masonry walls has caused a large fraction of the casualties in recent earthquakes. In spite of this, masonry is still the material of choice for housing construction in many seismically active areas. New masonry structures are commonly constructed with steel reinforcing bars. However, older buildings are often unreinforced or reinforced inadequately. Thus, there is a need for efficient and cost-effective methods for strengthening these types of structures.

Fiber-reinforced composites appear to offer a suitable solution. A thin layer of fiber-reinforced composites applied to unreinforced masonry walls in a wallpaper-like fashion (Figure 1) may be an effective strengthening mechanism as illustrated in Figure 2.

The test results shown in Figure 2 refer to a 1.2 m wide, 1.2 m tall and 10 cm thick wall made of red common bricks. The mortar applied between the bricks was made from Quikrete mortar mix combined with water in a ratio of six parts water to one part mixture. The reinforcement applied to both sides of the wall was chopped glass fiber mat reinforced with epoxy resin. A diagonal load was applied to the cured wall in accordance with ASTM standard E519-81. Forty-five cm wide reinforcement strips arranged in a cross shape increased the failure load of the walls by nearly 200%. The walls completely covered with

Composite Reinforcement “Wallpaper”

Fig. 1: “Wallpaper” composite reinforcement

Fig. 2: The failure loads of unreinforced and reinforced masonry walls subjected to diagonal loading

reinforcement could not be tested to failure since the failure load exceeded the 35 kN load capacity of the testing mechanism.

Since composites are effective reinforcements, as shown in Figure 2, several investigators have studied the behavior of masonry walls reinforced with composites. Most of the previous investigations have been experimental in nature [1-4] and few models have been developed to determine the performance of composite reinforced masonry [5]. In this investigation, an analytical procedure was developed to predict the behavior of masonry walls reinforced with composite sheets under combined in-plane normal and shear loads.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The model developed in this investigation considers solid walls, as well as walls with cutouts such as windows and doors, subjected to static, in-plane, normal and shear loads. Fiber-reinforced sheets are applied to either fully or partially cover one or both sides of the wall.

The model calculates the load set at which the wall fails and the deformation of the wall at the instant of failure.

The objective is to determine

- the relationship between the deformation of the wall and the magnitude of the applied normal and shear loads, and
- the load set under which both the masonry and the reinforcement fail.

MODEL

To model the behavior of a masonry building, each side of the building is treated separately and divided into wall units (Figure 3). Each wall unit is then subdivided into segments (Figure 4). In this investigation, four types of segments are considered

- rectangular segments reinforced with a cross shape, modeled as a truss (Figure 5)
- rectangular segments completely covered with the reinforcement, modeled as a truss (Figure 5)
- slender segments completely covered with the reinforcement, modeled as a beam (Figure 6)
- rectangular segments covered with the reinforcement containing an opening, modeled as a frame (Figure 7)

Fig. 3: Division of the masonry building into wall units

Fig. 4: Division of the wall unit into segments

Fig. 5: Cross-covered and fully covered wall segments modeled as a truss

Fig. 6: Slender, reinforced wall segment modeled as a beam

Fig. 7: Wall segment with an opening modeled as a frame

For each segment, the model provides the relation between the loads applied to the segment and the deformation of the segment, and the load set at which failure occurs. Each segment of a wall unit is considered separately and then combined to represent the entire wall. Details of the aforementioned models and the assembly procedure are given in references [6] and [7].

ILLUSTRATION OF THE MODEL

This model was used to evaluate the effectiveness of composites as a reinforcement for masonry. A parametric study was conducted to determine the increase in the load-carrying capacities of masonry walls when reinforced with different configurations of composites. In the present study, the composite used was chopped glass fibers embedded in an epoxy matrix.

To illustrate the use of the model, the behavior of a masonry wall was analyzed. The wall (13.3 m wide, 4.5 m high, 0.2 m thick) contains a window and a door, as shown in Figure 8. It is made of standard size (20 cm wide, 8 cm tall, 10 cm thick) fired clay building bricks and cement-lime mortar with the properties listed in Table 1. The walls are either unreinforced or reinforced on both sides with 1.3 mm thick epoxy/glass fiber mats with the patterns shown in Figure 8.

The wall is rigidly attached to the ground while a uniformly distributed normal load (400 kN) is applied along the top edge (Figure 9). A shear force V is also applied along the top edge. The magnitude of the shear load (V_f) and the horizontal deflection of the top left corner a (δ_f) are calculated.

The results, presented in Figure 10, indicate that an epoxy/glass fiber mat reinforcement increases substantially the load carrying capacity of the walls. The reinforced walls withstand a 3 – 4 times higher shear load than walls without any reinforcement, while the failure deflection of the reinforced walls are 20 – 30 higher than the failure of the unreinforced walls.

Fig. 8: Geometry of the masonry wall examined in the parametric study

Table 1: Material properties

Material	Young's Modulus (MPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)
Masonry assemblage	3200	-
Mortar	-	0.6
Epoxy / Glass fiber mat	5200	62.0

Fig. 9: Reinforcement patterns and loading of the wall examined in the parametric study

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the parametric study presented here suggest that epoxy/glass fiber mat reinforcements applied in wallpaper-like fashion should be an effective way of reducing damage to masonry buildings during earthquakes.

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Fig. 10: Load-carrying capacity and deflection at failure of masonry wall reinforced with different reinforcement patterns

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